

were three replications using two amendments. Chopped and dried rice and mustard *Brassica campestris* var. *Sarson* straws were added to equal 2% of the soil. Pots were located in normal field conditions and watered occasionally to supplement rainfall and provide average annual precipitation.

Soil columns were sampled at the end of the month using a standard soil-core sampler 2 cm in diameter and 18 cm deep. At each sample date, five soil cores were collected from each treatment, bulked in a paper bag, and air-dried in the laboratory. Five 50-g subsamples were taken from each bag and sclerotia were recovered by washing over 20- and 100-mesh screens. Sclerotia from each treatment were counted under a dissecting microscope and viability was tested by growing them on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at 3,000 ppm each under constant fluorescent light at 25±2° C.

Presence of organic matter reduced sclerotia survival — percent viability of sclerotia was less although total number

1. Effect of organic amendments on decline of sclerotia number.

2. Effect of organic amendments on germination of sclerotia.

of sclerotia had increased or remained constant over time. Burying sclerotia for 8 months in the presence of mustard reduced their number by 76% (Fig. 1) and viability by 75% (Fig. 2). Number and viability also declined in treatments without amendment, but after a few months germination ability stabilized at about 50%. Rice straw amendment

decreased number and viability in the beginning, but sclerotia increased at the end of the burial period (Fig. 1).

Rice residue seems to be a major factor in increasing the *S. oryzae* inoculum level in field soil. However, application of mustard organic matter will substantially reduce the inoculum level in the field.

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice yield losses to gall midge in North Thailand

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is one of the most economically important insect pests of rainfed wetland rice in Thailand. Granular insecticides are the only effective means of control, but they are expensive and require multiple applications to obtain satisfactory results. Gall midge infestations vary in Thailand and insecticide application should be based on the use of an economic threshold.

Experiments in farmers' fields at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, assessed yield losses caused by gall midge. A conventional

Gall midge infestation, yield components, and yield losses of 4 rice varieties at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, Thailand, 1979-81.^a

Variety	Insecticide treatment ^b	Infested tillers (%) 55-65 DT	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
1979						
RD1	Treated	1.0	11.4	5.5	2.3	—
RD1	Untreated	21.5	12.0	4.4	1.9	19
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Treated	2.2	10.7	4.6	2.7	—
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Untreated	26.5	10.9	4.4	2.5	8
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Treated	0.4	10.1	5.7	2.0	—
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Untreated	19.2	10.7	4.9	1.8	10
Leaung-Laung	Treated	1.8	7.1	4.5	2.9	—
Leaung-Laung	Untreated	25.0	11.5	3.1	1.9	33
1980						
RD1	Treated	6.3	9.7	6.0	1.8	—
RD1	Untreated	71.5	13.7	3.2	0.9	52
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Treated	1.4	8.1	6.0	2.5	—
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Untreated	68.9	11.1	3.8	1.5	42
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Treated	1.4	9.6	6.0	1.9	—
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Untreated	73.7	11.8	3.5	0.9	49
Leaung-Laung	Treated	0.6	8.1	5.7	2.5	—
Leaung-Laung	Untreated	61.1	12.2	3.6	1.2	50
1981						
RD1	Treated	9.8	11.8	8.9	3.1	—
RD1	Untreated	28.7	13.8	8.8	2.5	17

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experiment, using plots with and without insecticide, was used 1979-81 on four susceptible rice varieties — RD1, Leaug-Laung, Dawk-Ma-Li 105, and Niew-San-Pahtawng — in a strip plot design with three replications. In treated plots carbofuran (1 kg ai/ ha) was incorporated into the soil before planting and broadcast on paddy water 20 and 40 days after transplanting.

The second assessment method observed individual hills. Leaug-Laung was transplanted in a 0.08-ha field in 1981. Gall midge-infested tillers (silver-shoots) and total tillers were counted from 10 randomly selected rows/plot, 50 hills/row, 500 hills/ plot. Yield per hill was recorded. A wide range (0, 1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-30, 31-50, and 51-70%) of infestation levels which could be correlated with yield were obtained with this method.

Results from the conventional insecticide plot method showed potential yields varied annually, possibly because of weather factors (see table). Relating rice yield to gall midge infestations was unsuccessful because it would require many years to get a wide range of gall midge infestation levels. High gall midge infestation (average of 69% infested tillers) occurred in 1980. Yield reduction in all varieties ranged from 42 to 50%. Less damage (22-23%) occurred in 1979 and 1981. Yield loss variation was greater at lower levels of infestation. In most cases Niew-San-Pahtawng and Dawk-Ma-Li 105 showed lowest losses. Gall midge infestation induced rice tillering, and there were more tillers in untreated plots than in treated ones but panicle number was small.

Results from the single hill experiment demonstrated that tiller number increased gradually with increasing gall

TABLE CONTINUED

Variety	Insecticide treatment ^b	Infested tillers (%) 55-65 DT	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Treated	1.6	8.5	6.8	3.6	—
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Untreated	16.2	9.3	5.5	2.8	22
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Treated	3.7	10.8	8.1	3.2	—
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Untreated	21.9	12.3	7.6	2.9	10
Leaug-Laung	Treated	3.7	8.8	7.1	3.1	—
Leaug-Laung	Untreated	20.2	9.9	6.7	2.1	13

^aAv of 3 replications. Insect damage and yield components were measured from 30 random hills. DT = days after transplanting. ^b1 kg ai carbofuran/ha was incorporated into the soil before transplanting, and broadcast 20 and 40 DT, except in 1979 trial when only 2 broadcast applications (20 and 40 DT) were made.

midge infestation (see figure). The general yield loss equation was $Y = 5.118 + 0.52 X$ (when $Y = \% \text{ yield loss}$ and $X = \% \text{ silvershoots}$). When this equation was used to determine average yield loss for the four rice varieties, the results closely agreed with those of the conventional method.

Data showed average potential rice yield was 2.64 t/ha. Using the yield loss equation, yield reduction at 20% gall

midge infestation is 15.6% or 411 kg/ha, costing \$57.5 (when 1 t rice = \$140) in lost production. Two applications of carbofuran cost \$57.2 (1 kg of carbofuran = \$0.86). Therefore, treating infestation levels above 20% will give a return benefit to cover the cost of control. Because annual gall midge infestation of rice at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, is more than 20%, insecticide application is economic.. ✎

Relationships between percent gall midge infestation and number of tillers and yield loss in Leaug-Laung rice variety at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, 1981.

Leersia hexandra as weed host for the brown planthopper

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* that normally develops on *Leersia hexandra* weed has been found at two sites on the IRRI farm. Incuba-

tion period and egg hatchability were tested in 10 replications.

Five gravid females were enclosed in each 6- × 30-cm mylar cage and allowed to oviposit for 24 hours on *Leersia* plants. The insects were removed and nymphs that hatched were counted and removed daily. When hatching terminated, plants were dissected and unhatched eggs counted.

BPH longevity and fecundity were also studied. Pairs of newly emerged adults were placed on potted *Leersia* in a mylar cage. Insects that died were counted and removed daily. Living insects were transferred every 3 to 4 days to fresh host plants. Plants from which adults were removed were dissected and eggs were counted.

Incubation period was 7.8 days, egg